

A Study on Television Advertisement on Consumer Buying Behaviour at Darling Electronics Pvt Ltd, Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

Television advertising helps to make the product appealing to a person's basic motives and influence their behaviour and attitude towards the product. Advertisement assumes a noteworthy job in inducing, educating and reminding both potential and existing customers towards settling on buying behaviour. It plays a vital role in shaping dreams and aspirations and helps the customer to take conscious product and brand decisions. The main objective of the study is to find the association between gender of the respondent and factors influence advertisement on consumer behaviour. In this study Primary and secondary data was used for analyzing the data. Questionnaire was used to collect primary data. In this study 80 samples are selected at random from a population of 100 customers. The data were analyzed using the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation and chi-square. Suitable suggestions and conclusions were made from the findings of the study.

KEYWORDS: Advertisement, Consumer Buying Behaviour

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INTRODUCTION

In the present period of data blast and the universe of media, Advertisements assume a noteworthy job in changing the behaviour and attitude of customers towards the items appeared in the advertisements. The advertisements not just change the method for item is devoured by customer however modifies the attitude with which they take a gander at the item. Everywhere throughout the world, promotions have been utilized since ages for a wide influence of brands. For in the course of the most recent two decades, a sharp increment in advertisements per brand can be seen. Advertisements have extraordinary impact in obtaining choice of clients for specific brands. The present investigation focuses on identifying the influence of advertisements on the consumer behaviour and attitude with uncommon reference to consumer durables.

An Advertisement is one of the topical procedures of numerous brands for the advancement of their item. The motivation behind mass advertisements is to pick up consideration for the item, guaranteeing delayed relationship with shoppers, or with the end goal of review of their item in customers mind. Customer purchasing conduct is generally influenced by certain components which incorporate culture, family and brand picture. Then

again brand awareness additionally encourages the customer to purchase a specific item. Because of this reality, a corrective organization focuses on promoting the items. This report additionally put light on different elements such as impact the purchasing behaviour of the customer, for example, ways of life, acquiring power, innovation, customary culture and pay. Sponsors spend much measure of speculation while promoting their item so they maintain their attention on these variables so they can impact consumer mind with advertisements. Advertisement helps the company to create the awareness in their customers and ingredients the advertisements shape the perception of the customers either in the positive or in a negative way. Individuals can see the nature of the items by social event the data which they typically get past advertisements. Marketers are focusing customer decide that is customer is their first preference.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

NAVEEN RAI (2013) Consumer attitude and behaviour tremendously affected by advertisements, as model Life Good (LG) and Samsung are the brands that are most well known in Indian market because of the commercials, then again Onida the old brand which use to give huge deals in mid-1990's needed deals because of less notices,

according to their assembling of items with wide go and less on cost, yet at the same time not are taste for purchasers. This reflect the behavioural change and attitude formation of consumer as Onida is as yet giving wide scope of items yet shoppers just use to go for other new marks because of their better commercial techniques including Sports and Bollywood celebrities who go about as icons in minds of Indian people. Durables as well as nourishment items and refreshments, and so on., likewise get affected by advertisements.

GUPTA (2014) in the present period, advertisers are focusing customer decide that is customer is their first preference. To watch out for customers the main responsibility to the association is to pick up the learning about the customers. In this way advertisers will be effective in satisfying the requirements and needs of the customers and look for the better opportunities in the market. Researchers find out that advertisers need to comprehend these four things so as to serve their customers better. Initially advertisers must realize that customers settle on rational decision so they can get the best item available in the market. Besides customers additionally settle on unreasonable choices and they are imprudent and can be attracted towards the promotional activities. Similarly, enthusiastic affiliation additionally put an influence on the minds of customers.

GUNJAN BAHET (2015), Advertisement is an Endeavour at creativity which influences the customer's motive to purchase a specific item and change or make the impression of the item in the minds of the consumers. Advertisement appeal act as a provider to stimulate the psychological motive of the consumer for purchasing. Promotion includes rational and enthusiastic interests. In level headed interests the item can be stressed primarily on its advantages and the issues. It can solve while on other hand emotional appeal meet the consumer's mind, emotional and social necessities.

YASIR RAFIQUE (2014) contended that advertisement is an approach to communicate with the audience. They accepted that culture exceptionally impact the purchasing practices of the individuals in light of the fact that each individual has various needs and patterns as per their ways of life. In this manner in the event that we state that advertisement resembles an enchantment than it won't be false on the grounds that advertisement really changes the requirements and needs of the individuals and now and again it makes the need among the individuals People are exceptionally influenced by the notices and associations are attempting to focus on the majority of the individuals. Organizations are utilizing over the line and underneath the line methods of the commercial which fit best with their items.

NIDHI KOTWAL (2008), a research conducted in India found that young people are profoundly pulled in towards the TV advertisement. Along this school young girl affected by the TV commercials and they will in general purchase the items which they found in advertisements.

So, it gives us thought that broad communications has the extraordinary effect on the notices. Associations are moving towards the inventive substance which draws in

the adolescent young ladies just as young men to purchase the items.

RAJU (2013), With the cutting edge time there has been seen a noteworthy blast in innovation, with this innovation promoters presently considering the quantity of broad communications channels and methods for interchanges which give them the simple and quick access to the purchasers. Opposite side of this innovation progression is that customers are currently having a lot of data and they can get the thing which best suits to them. So it turns out to be hard for the promoter to manufacture the brand awareness and condition the minds of the customers to settle on definite buy choice, as customers are dealing with the items and data.

POPE (2009), Role of advertisement is to convey message to the far distances. It is also use to focus on the dissipate mass group of spectators. The role of advertising on sales volume is significant. It is demonstrated to be fundamental apparatus in upgrading the offers of brand. Advertisement is directly connected with the offers of the items. Through advertisement customer conduct formed and they spur to purchase such items. Scientists found that repetition in the promotion hit the minds of the customers which likewise help them to recollect that item and buy more than once.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To find impact of television advertisement on consumer buying behaviors at DARLING ELECTRONICS LTD.
2. To study factors affecting the consumer buying process with respect to television advertisements.
3. To determine an association between gender of the respondent and level of impact of television advertisement.
4. To find the significant relationship between age of the respondent and television advertisement.

HYPOTHESIS:

1. **H₀**: There is no association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.
H_a: There is association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.
2. **H₀**: There is no significant relationship between age of the respondent and television advertisement.
H_a: There is significant relationship between age of the respondent and television advertisement.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is an arrangement that indicates the objectives of the investigation, technique to be received in the gathering of the information, tools in analysis of information and supportive to frame hypothesis. A research design is the arrangement of action of condition for gathering and investigation of information in a way that plans to combine relevance to research reason with economy in method. Research design includes a progression of objective basic leadership decisions identifying with choices in regards to the motivation behind the examination, where the investigation will be

directed, what kind of study it should be, and the worldly parts of the study.

TYPE OF RESEARCH

Descriptive research

Descriptive research includes survey and fact-finding enquiries of various types. The significant motivation behind descriptive research is description of the situation as it exists at present. In sociology and business examine we regularly utilize the term Ex post facto research for descriptive research thinks about. The primary characteristic of this strategy is that the analyst has no power over the factors; he can just report what has occurred or what's going on.

SAMPLE SIZE AND TECHNIQUES

SIMPLE RANDOM SAMPLING

A simple random sampling is the basic sampling technique where we select a gathering of subjects (an example) for concentrate from a bigger gathering information. Every individual is picked totally by some coincidence and every individual from the populace has an equivalent possibility of being incorporated into the example.

DATA COLLECTION

1. PRIMARY DATA

The information which are gathered new, unique in character is called essential information. Data were gathered through questionnaire from employees of DARLING ELECTRONICS PVT LIMITED.

2. SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data is information gathered by somebody other than the user. In this study the secondary data was gathered from the books, journals, and websites and company records.

INSTRUMENTS OF DATA COLLECTION

QUESTIONNAIRE

The questions are arranged in logical sequences. The questionnaire consists of open and close ended questions presented to the employees for their response. Likert's scale used in constructing the questionnaire.

- 5- Strongly Agree 4- Agree 3- Neutral
- 2- Disagree 1- Strongly Disagree

STATISTICAL TOOLS:

CHI-SQUARE TEST:

In this project chi- square test was used. This is an analysis of technique which analyzed the stated data in the project. It analysis the assumed data and calculated in the study. The chi-square test is an important test amongst the several tests of significant developed by statistical. Chi-square, symbolically written as x² measure used in the context of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance.

Therefore, there is no association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.

TABLE NO: 2 ANALYSES USING KARL PEARSON COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age of respondent and factors affecting the consumers in television advertisement.

H_a: There is significant relationship between age of respondent and factors affecting the consumers in television advertisement.

FORMULA:

$$X^2 = \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where,

O_i = Observed frequency

E_i = Expected frequency

KARL PEARSON COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

It is widely used mathematical method where in the numerical expression use to calculate the degree and direction of the relationship between the linear related variables.

Pearson's method, popularly known as a **Pearson's correlation**, is the most extensively used quantitative method in practice. The coefficient of correlation is denoted by 'r'.

The relationship between two variables X and Y is to be ascertained, then the following formula is used,

FORMULA:

$$\text{Coefficient of correlation, } r = \frac{\sum ((x-dx)(y-dy))}{\sqrt{\sum(x-dx)^2 * \sum(y-dy)^2}}$$

DATA INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1 CHI - SQUARE ANALYSIS FOR GENDER OF RESPONDENT AND FACTORS INFLUENCING TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT

H₀: There is no association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.

H_a: There is association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.

Gender	Factors Influence in Television Advertisement			Total
	Low	Moderate	High	
Male	0	16	29	45
Female	0	16	19	35
Total	0	32	48	80

Chi square calc = 0.847

Degree of Freedom = 4

LS = 5% (0.05)

P value = 0.538

INFERENCE

Since the calculated value of x² (**0.847**) > the table value (**0.538**) of x², H₀ is accepted.

X	Y	x-dx	y-dy	(x-dx)^2	(y-dy)^2	(x-dx)(y-dy)
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
1	11	-1.725	-2.325	121	2.975625	360.050625
2	16	-0.725	2.675	256	0.525625	134.56
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
1	13	-1.725	-0.325	169	2.975625	502.880625
3	11	0.275	-2.325	121	0.075625	9.150625
3	11	0.275	-2.325	121	0.075625	9.150625
1	17	-1.725	3.675	289	2.975625	859.955625
3	15	0.275	1.675	225	0.075625	17.015625
2	16	-0.725	2.675	256	0.525625	134.56
4	15	1.275	1.675	225	1.625625	365.765625
4	16	1.275	2.675	256	1.625625	416.16
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
2	15	-0.725	1.675	225	0.525625	118.265625
1	15	-1.725	1.675	225	2.975625	669.515625
1	14	-1.725	0.675	196	2.975625	583.2225
3	15	0.275	1.675	225	0.075625	17.015625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	13	0.275	-0.325	169	0.075625	12.780625
2	13	-0.725	-0.325	169	0.525625	88.830625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	14	1.275	0.675	196	1.625625	318.6225
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
2	14	-0.725	0.675	196	0.525625	103.0225
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
3	12	0.275	-1.325	144	0.075625	10.89
3	13	0.275	-0.325	169	0.075625	12.780625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	13	1.275	-0.325	169	1.625625	274.730625
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
3	13	0.275	-0.325	169	0.075625	12.780625
2	13	-0.725	-0.325	169	0.525625	88.830625
2	13	-0.725	-0.325	169	0.525625	88.830625
2	14	-0.725	0.675	196	0.525625	103.0225
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
2	15	-0.725	1.675	225	0.525625	118.265625
3	12	0.275	-1.325	144	0.075625	10.89
4	16	1.275	2.675	256	1.625625	416.16
2	14	-0.725	0.675	196	0.525625	103.0225
1	10	-1.725	-3.325	100	2.975625	297.5625
2	11	-0.725	-2.325	121	0.525625	63.600625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	13	0.275	0.325	169	0.075625	12.780625
3	13	0.275	-0.325	169	0.075625	12.780625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	14	1.275	0.675	196	1.625625	318.6225
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	11	0.275	-2.325	121	0.075625	9.150625
2	13	-0.725	-0.325	169	0.525625	88.830625
2	13	-0.725	-0.325	169	0.525625	88.830625
3	12	0.275	-1.325	144	0.075625	10.89
4	9	1.275	-4.325	81	1.625625	131.675625
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	15	1.275	1.675	225	1.625625	365.765625
3	16	0.275	2.675	256	0.075625	19.36
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	13	1.275	-0.325	169	1.625625	274.730625
2	14	-0.725	0.675	196	0.525625	103.0225

4	14	1.275	0.675	196	1.625625	318.6225
3	12	0.275	-1.325	144	0.075625	10.89
4	14	1.275	0.675	196	1.625625	318.6225
2	10	-0.725	-3.325	100	0.525625	52.5625
2	10	-0.725	-3.325	100	0.525625	52.5625
2	16	-0.725	2.675	256	0.525625	134.56
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
4	11	1.275	-2.325	121	1.625625	196.700625
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
1	15	-1.725	1.675	225	2.975625	669.515625
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
3	14	0.275	0.675	196	0.075625	14.8225
4	13	1.275	-0.325	169	1.625625	274.730625
3	10	0.275	-3.325	100	0.075625	7.5625
1	10	-1.725	-3.325	100	2.975625	297.5625
1	12	-1.725	-1.325	144	2.975625	428.49
218	1066			14502	59.95	10877.66375

$$\text{Coefficient of correlation, } r = \frac{\sum ((x-dx)(y-dy))}{\sqrt{(\sum(x-dx)^2 * \sum(y-dy)^2)}}$$

$$r = \frac{11.875}{\sqrt{(1980.75)(483.3875)}}$$

Coefficient of correlation r = 0.046047

INFERENCE

The value of correlation r = 0.046047. This shows that there exists a positive correlation between age of respondent and factors affecting the consumers in television advertisement. Hence, null hypothesis can be rejected and alternative hypothesis was accepted. It was found that there is a relationship between age of respondent and television advertisement.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. By using chi square analysis, it was found that the calculated value of χ^2 (**0.847**) > the table value (**0.538**) of χ^2 , H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is significant association between gender of respondent and factors influencing in television advertisement.
2. From the correlation analysis it was found that there exists a positive correlation between age of respondent and factors affecting the consumers in television advertisement.

Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis. It was found that there is a relationship between age of respondent and factors affecting the consumers in television advertisement.

SUGGESTIONS

1. It is suggested to the company that they can make use of famous celebrity for advertisement of their product to reach the customers effectively.
2. A creative and innovative way of television advertisement must be adopted to catch the attention of the consumers.

3. It is suggested that Consumer durables are categorized by affordable costs, long life so advertisements should be designed in such a way that it is more informative, simple, clear and transparent.
4. Special advertisement can be telecasted stating the discounts and special offers to attract the customers.
5. Demand for consumer durables at darling electronics has been increasing because of rising income, increasing urbanization changing lifestyle so organizations have to design promotion activities to tap this huge market.

CONCLUSION

Advertising has become important factors which influence the customer buying behaviour. The object of the study is to find impact of television advertisement on consumer buying behaviours at DARLING ELECTRONICS LTD. It was found that by using chi square, there is significant correlation between age of the respondent and television advertisement. By using chi square, there is significant association between gender of respondent and factors influencing television advertisement.

It is suggested to the company that they can make use of famous celebrity for advertisement of their product to reach the customers effectively. A creative and innovative way of television advertisement must be adopted to catch the attention of the consumers. Special advertisement can be telecasted stating the discounts and special offers to attract the customers.

From this study it can be concluded that the Advertising is one of the most successful ingredients to attract customer to their products and brands. This study applied the

correlation and chi-square to check the stationary of the data used in the analysis. The correlation coefficient r is a measure of the linear relationship between two attributes or columns of data was used to analyze the long run relationship among the variables techniques to estimates advertising has positive relation with customer buying behavior. the advertising and other explanatory variables that affect the dependent variables. The results of this analysis showed that

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